

A New Procedure for Preparing Isothiocyanates: Pyrolysis of Alkyl Dithiourethanes

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Pyrolysis of alkyl dithiourethanes has been shown to result in the formation of related isothiocyanate and mercaptan. The yields of isothiocyanates average 62 to 92% and the procedure is of preparatory value.

SINCE isothiocyanates are an important group of organic compounds several methods are available for their preparation¹. Quite a few of these use salts of dithiocarbamic acids as starting material; for example, reaction of these with lead² or ferric salts, ethyl chloroformate³⁻⁵, phosgene⁴ and sodium hypochlorite⁶ are wellknown preparatory methods.

Formation of isothiocyanates on pyrolysis of esters of dithiocarbamic acids has been reported in a few cases⁷⁻¹⁰ but this does not appear to have received the attention it deserved. It has now been found that if alkyl dithiocarbamates with an alkyl-/aryl-substituent on nitrogen are pyrolysed at temperatures higher than their melting points, related mercaptan is eliminated and an almost pure residue of the

TABLE 1. PYROLYSIS OF THE ALKYL ESTERS OF DITHIOCARBAMIC ACIDS

In every experiment 10.0 g of the ester of dithiocarbamic acid was heated for 2.5 to 6 hr (until evolution of mercaptan ceased).

Sr. No.	Ester of dithiocarbamic acid pyrolysed	Temp. of pyrolysis °C	Residue left behind (Isothiocyanate) g	Thiocarbamide formed with ammonia/amine g	Yield per cent computed on thiocarbamide formed	Yield per cent on steam-distillation
1	Ethyl phenyldithiocarbamate, m.p. 60° (lit. ⁷ m.p. 61°).	145	Phenyl-6.5	Phenyl-7.2	93	87
2	Ethyl <i>p</i> -tolylidithiocarbamate, m.p. 72° (lit. ⁹ m.p. 74°).	170	<i>p</i> -Tolyl-6.5	<i>p</i> -Tolyl-7.2	92	85
3	Ethyl <i>p</i> -chlorophenyldithiocarbamate, m.p. 85° (Found : N, 6.0; S, 27.2%; C ₉ H ₁₀ NS ₂ Cl requires : N, 6.0; S, 27.6%).	175	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-6.5	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-7.1	89	82
4	Ethyl <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyldithiocarbamate, m.p. 77° (lit. ¹³ m.p. 77°).	160	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-6.6	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-7.0	87	85
5	Ethyl benzylidithiocarbamate, m.p. 50° (lit. ¹⁴ m.p. 52°).	175	Benzyl-5.3	1,3-Dibenzyl-9.0	74	71
6	Methyl methylidithiocarbamate, ¹⁴	160	Methyl-5.0	Methyl-6.2	83	79
7	Ethyl ethylidithiocarbamate ¹⁴	185	Ethyl-5.0	Ethyl-6.0	85	77
8	Ethyl <i>n</i> -butylidithiocarbamate, b.p. 110°/15 mm.	160	<i>n</i> -Butyl-4.5	<i>n</i> -Butyl-6.0	80	62
9	Ethyl cyclohexylidithiocarbamate, b.p. 120°/15 mm.	180	Cyclohexyl-5.0	1,3-Dicyclohexyl-8.8	74	65
10	Ethyl 1-naphthyldithiocarbamate, m.p. 125° (Found : N, 5.5; S, 25.3%; C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NS ₂ requires : N, 5.6; S, 25.9%).	160	1-Naphthyl-7.2	1,3-Di-1-naphthyl-11.6	83	85
11	Ethyl 2-naphthyldithiocarbamate, m.p. 135° (Found : N, 5.6; S, 25.7%; C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NS ₂ requires : N, 5.6; S, 25.9%).	160	2-Naphthyl-7.0	1,3-Di-2-naphthyl-11.0	82	80
12	Methyl 2-aminopyridyldithiocarbamate ¹⁵ .	170	2-Pyridyl-6.0	1,3-Di-2-Pyridyl-10.0	80	—
13	Ethyl 2-aminopyridyldithiocarbamate, m.p. 70° (Found : N, 13.8; S, 32.0%; C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ requires : N, 14.1; S, 32.3%).	175	2-Pyridyl-6.0	1-(2-Pyridyl)-3-phenyl-9.0	83	—

corresponding isothiocyanate is left behind. The reaction, in fact, can be looked upon as a reversal of the addition of mercaptans to isothiocyanates leading to dithiourethanes^{1,7,10-12}. The pyrolysis has been studied in over a dozen cases and the yields of isothiocyanates isolated on steam distillation of the residue or estimated as thiocarbamides on reaction with ammonia/amine range between 62 to 92%. The reaction primarily is one as expressed by the following reaction :

Only traces of Hydrogen sulphide were detected in the mercaptan which is the sole gaseous product and can be absorbed in a trap containing alkali. In the case of ethyl ester no ethylene could be detected or no free amine or thiocarbamide was found in the residues.

In the preparation of amine or ammonium salts of dithiocarbamic acids difficulties are often encountered in isolating these under economic conditions. The formation and isolation of esters is relatively easier as these can be isolated directly by carrying out the reaction of amine, carbon disulphide and alkyl halide in presence of a base.

The results of the pyrolytic experiments are summarised in the table.

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